

SUGGESTIONS FOR TEACHING AND LEARNING SEMANTIC AND TEXTUAL RELATIONS TO FOREIGN STUDENTS

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Lidia STRAH¹,
Universitatea de Stat din Moldova

ABSTRACT. Linguistic principles of the text at different levels are very important when teaching foreign language and the typical aspects of the text are meant to form a communicative competency. The requirements for the explanation and summarizing texts deal with the development of communication skills and with an interpretation oriented to an accessible communication of the foreign student.

Keywords: content elements, directing elements, surface structures

Introduction

Today, when we live in a time of changes, when the human being is looking for new meanings for his life, understanding of the contemporary world is based on the communicative act – as a primary act. In this regard, the language acquisition (in our case the Romanian language) implies the activation of an action type scheme, which focuses on both general competences and specific competences of the student, formed and developed based on various formative elements. One of the elements is the instructive text as a determinative factor, since by its very essence as a communication phenomenon it implies the perception from the part of the student of the context he/she has to act in.

Therefore, text linguistics principles at different levels are of great importance in teaching a foreign language. One of these principles is the principle of phrasal presentation of the text reflected in the description of the linguistic means used for expressing the relation between the utterances.

Thus, the use of the definite article in German, English and French shall be explained in terms of defining or not defining the object and, consequently, it is common the use of terms that substitute certain words in a sentence, factor which is, as a rule, the object of grammatical and lexical explanation.

Hence, the indications regarding the distinctions of their application are realized in the process of education, being learned through exercises; let's compare, for example, the form and use of the possessive pronoun:

Table 1

Form and use of the possessive pronoun

German	Sein	Ihr	ihre		lui	Ei	lor
English	His	her	their	Romanian	său	Sa	
French	Son	sa	ses		său	Sa	la

Morphemes and the periphrastic constructions which express the time, mode, aspect of the action are learnt in the same way, even though when making the rules, the situation aspect or the relational aspect between the sentences is not correspondingly considered.

The languages examined have also certain basic elements of the sentence and, often, coincide as to function and structure; for example, intonation, stress, emphasis and contraposition,

¹ **Lidia STRAH**, Facultatea de Litere, Universitatea de Stat din Moldova, Chişinău, Republica Moldova, strahlidia@gmail.com, +37369077943

consequence of the parts of the sentence, topic and comment relation. The workbooks pay special attention to the differences between them (compare the intonation in attributive and disjunctive-interrogative sentences in English), the use of periphrastic structures instead on emphasis in English and French: *It's he who...*, *C'est lui qui...*, in German: *Er ist...*, in Romanian: *El...*

In this context, it can be mentioned that the expressive means are also known in all the languages and often coincide. The affirmative answer to the question that consists of one sentence is generally a common phenomenon. The requirement to answer with a full sentence, often present when teaching a foreign language, can be justified and tolerated from the point of view of the language teaching theory, from the communicative perspective, but, such answers are not recommended. When teaching a foreign language it is necessary, first of all, to communicate the lexical means that correspond to the text, without giving any additional „textual grammar”. This fact also corresponds to the principles referring to the semantic-textual relations and to the communicative-practical laws. Recovering of the key-words through the elements that replace them, such as synonyms, antonyms, explanations, is a common phenomenon in all the languages. However, the main aspect is the knowledge of the synonyms and possible explanations, and the factors of the speech situation become known to the student from the experience of different situation from his/her own culture.

Other aspects typical for the text, such as: thematic and logical separation, adjustment of communication based on the adequate character of the intentions and the situations of use are not destined to be communicated immediately to the foreign students who have already a speech competence.

The theoretical principles referring to the text shall determine, mostly, their setting up into the didactic materials (first of all in the workbooks) and into the teaching methods of the teacher. It is always necessary to direct the work of the foreign students, in order to obtain explicit communicative theoretical and textual knowledge, but, firstly, it is very important to form the verbal communication skills. The process of discovering the peculiarities of the text from the point of view of the method of teaching Romanian to foreign students includes the examination of the text as:

- basis for obtaining certain linguistic and encyclopedic knowledge;
- teaching means for different types of verbal/oral activity (listening, speaking, reading, writing);
- the appreciated and learned result of the teaching-learning process which implies learning and teaching.

For the process of teaching foreign students as basis serve the texts that:

- contain valuable information explaining the reasons;
- correspond to the interests and perception possibilities of the foreign students from a certain group, according to the age and teaching course;
- contain materials in Romanian which shall be used and which shall be learned by the foreign students in order to develop their communication skills;
- contain means used for the formation and development of communication intentions;
- contain logical-object and verbal-situation models.

Based on these findings, we can affirm that the didactic texts shall be structured in dependence of the goal and theme they have. When choosing the text it is necessary to consider the language, content and the methodical organization, and, thus, the texts can be classified as follows;

- monologue-text, dialogue-text or mixed texts depending on the number of students involved in the communication activity;
- informative, descriptive and narrative texts;
- communication texts of everyday/daily, publicist, science popular, literary and artistic character from the functional and stylistic perspective;

- texts containing new or partially reduced information;
- text containing a certain number of unknown or un signaled lexical and grammatical phenomena from the perspective of the structure of the spoken language;
- texts destined for speaking, writing, listening and reading – after the speaking activity carried out together with the teaching-learning process of the Romanian as a foreign language;

All these types of texts are and shall obligatorily form the basis when planning the teaching process by the teacher. In certain conditions (linguistic and contextual coincidence of the possibilities of learning the language) these types of texts can be, at the same time, the contents and means of the teaching and learning processes, especially when speaking about reading and listening. The basic text (from the workbook or the information from a newspaper) usually needs a methodical intervention in order to become an efficient source of knowledge and to develop the communication skills of the foreign students. Such a text, named text-reference, shall:

- capture the attention of the foreign students;
- describe actual, interesting, important facts and events from the pragmatic perspective;
- have an initiating structure which would allow students to learn the content and the significance of the unknown linguistic material through the so-called extra-linguistic means, particularly through mimics, gestures and other concrete or intuitive teaching means.

The *text-reference* can be used in the form of communication from the part of the teacher, recorded communication, as a text for reading or conversation between the teacher and the student. Consequently, the text can be paraphrased or can appear spontaneously during the communication process between the teacher and the foreign student, pursuant to a goal-targeted planning.

The *text-reference* can be consolidated or supplemented depending on its content, linguistic and instructional educational orientation. In this regard, it is especially necessary:

- to form chains of reference words and write them on the blackboard or on a tape in order to explain the thematic relation, as well as the lexical and grammatical means of textual coherence;
- to break in the answer by an additional question in order to check out the level of understanding;
- to request the students to repeat certain sentences in order to strengthen the knowledge and form the habit of using them automatically.

The message of the text presupposes not the content as such, but the expressive unit together with its linguistic form and informational content, present in any communication act.

Thus, the so-called *summarizing explanation text*, as a result of the communication, shall demonstrate both the teacher and the foreign student:

- the level of substantiality and assimilation of linguistic means, used, requested and expected within the text and, thus, the level of correctness and conformity with the norm;
- the level of skills to do freely and in several ways the exercise given in accordance with the thematic orientation and content;
- the ability to correctly realize the communication concepts under the linguistic and situational perspective (inventions, appraisals).

Within the activities on a certain topic, the summarizing explanation texts can have a distinct level of speech and content variants, to wit a departure from the text-reference.

These can contain the materials from the summarizing applicative texts and can direct to the next text on the basis of a new orientation of the initial goal. In this regard, the texts shall be accompanied by the corresponding tasks and exercises.

The numerous requirements towards the summarizing explanation texts can be submitted by the teacher with the aim of differentiation or stimulation of the learning results of the Romanian by foreign students. When making the task and the requirements it should be considered the group atmosphere as it can generate, rarely, a careless communication environment. In an "adequate"

environment, communication constitutes the result of the lack of information, of the need to exchange the views and existing divergences. A communication event serves, in each case, the satisfaction of certain personal or socially determined needs. In the process of teaching foreign students, the need of communicating and informing the students, presented in texts, shall be methodically directed. The task given by the teacher is determined by instructional and educational goals, by the development of speaking skills substantiated both theoretically and practically, as well as the necessary procedures for revision and consolidation of the material. When building summarizing explanation text a special attention is given to lexical and grammar means which the students can apply in practice to the extent they possess the language.

Table 2

Methods of presenting semantic and textual relations

The development of a verbal strategy depends mostly on the manner the foreign students can present schematically the task they have to learn.

The summarizing explanation text aimed at contriving the level of speaking abilities shall be, as a rule, provided with auxiliary indices. These can be:

a) presentation of content references when wording the communication task (CT) within the limits of an oral answer in Romanian (" Speak about the home town, mentioning, at the same time, its geographical location, main companies and what they produce, as well as the town's rarities and curiosities");

b) if necessary, additional means;

c) demonstration of visual fine-art stimulants (pictures, drawings etc.)

The next step could facilitate the combination of various auxiliary references. When wording the text, the data can be repeated, reminded or supplemented.

In the suggested chart, it can be seen that the conditions for supplementing the text's task (description, communication) are presented in a very simple manner.

For accessibility, the *directing elements* (DE), used by the teacher are noted down before the partial solution found by the student, resulted from the *content elements* (CE), regardless of the fact if the directing element has been presented before or during the activity of the student. The broken arrows indicate on the possible variants of transformation of the directing element, of the content element, expression element, units D1 or D2 or various correcting actions.

Through the teacher's actions the foreign student receives an instruction which urges him to achieve, accordingly, a task of *productive communication* (PC) in Romanian. For this purpose the student shall be announced, through an acknowledgment, about the expected situational and communication result. The presentation of various detailed elements allows the student to clarify the teacher's expectations and understand that these distinct results are essential for evaluation. In the actions of the foreign student the *directing elements* (DE) are being transformed into *content elements* (CE) according to individual premises and are formulated in the sentences (S) of interior monologue. In case of uncertainty concerning the knowledge of Romanian, these are also accompanied by the intermediary actions in the mother tongue, *surface structures* (D1E1). The surface structure of Romanian (D1E2) is, by including D1E1, a direct translation or the results of adaptation of the foreign students to the possibilities offered by the competence of knowledge of Romanian language as a foreign language for expression. *Verification* (V1) of the own results may influence the choice and order of the content elements following the planned expression, in this regard, or the realization of the further speech. The *teacher's verification actions* (VD1) generate, in certain cases, the following directing actions and lead to the assessment of the foreign student's level of learning.

Thereby the final result of development of the student's communication skills (in the synthesis explanatory text) reflects, first of all, his capacity to correctly use, in accordance with the task given, the means of the Romanian language from the semantic, grammatical and practical point of view. The foreign student shows the level of learning of the functional elements and of the rules contained in the system of Romanian language and the manner he can use them to achieve the communication task as a given text.

Knowing the rules established by means of theoretical and linguistic researches of the text, pertaining to the thematic and content structure of various text categories, as well as to the conditions of their formation, adequate to the initial concept, are the essential premises for the fundamental scientific organization of the main and introductory texts, of wording the communication tasks. As a rule, the linguistic principles of the text do not consider the methodical and pedagogical conditions which imply an interpretation oriented to a well determined goal, in order to become important for pedagogical goals.

In the process of interpreting the text, the pragmatic composition of the student is very important; it includes the functional use of linguistic resources based on action schemes. Thus, rational and fundamental methodical application of the texts requires a methodically substantiated research. It shall learn the text depending on its philological and general education, and depending

on the formation and thoroughness of the elements in accordance with the foreign students' belief and concepts about the world.

Conclusions

At the same time, the researches shall aim at developing conditions that would correspond to the logics of the teaching process and, based on this, to conclude regarding the choice, organization and adaptation of the text, the system of exercises necessary for the consolidation of the knowledge of the language and the measures of conduct with the aim to interiorize the rules and lexical, grammatical, structural and content elements, as well as communicative elements. At the same time, the general communication skills of the foreign students shall be considered, including the skills of using the Romanian language.

But, not all the linguistic principles of the text are compulsory in the same manner for the methodical work. Thus, certain phenomena require a special attention due to a high risk of interference.

Based on the integration of different ideas, there has been made only certain general conclusions regarding the structures and functions of the text and preparation of the foreign students for the work on it.

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